

The Stone-Gardening Game – Full Facilitation Guide

Figure 1: FESTIVAL OF FUTURE NOWS 2025, Neue Nationalgalerie – Berlin, 31.10. – 02.11.2025. A collaboration of the Neue Nationalgalerie – Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz and the Institut für Raumexperimente e. V. Photo: Yanina Isla / @yaninaisla

The stone-gardening game is intended to offer students a safe yet playful first encounter through low-stakes, non-verbal collaboration. It consists of a building phase and a reflection phase, as well as a facilitated sharing/discussion. On the following pages we provide everything you need to set it up and facilitate it alongside some inspiration on how to adapt it to different teaching contexts.

1. Materials, Setup, and Rules

1.1. Materials

Per groups of three to five:

- One large plate filled with sand
- Ca. 50 stones of varied size and shape
- Printed/virtually available written instructions as given below

Several groups can play at the same time; larger plates might allow for more members in one group.

1.2. Duration

- 10-20 min to build the stone garden
- A few minutes of silent reflection on a provided set of questions
- 10-15 min sharing in group
- Possibly 10-15 minutes sharing/discussion in plenum

1.3. Written instructions

- Get together in groups of three to five around one plate. Decide on a first player.
- First player: Choose a stone and place it, adjusting its position until it's right.
- Next player: Add a stone by following the request of the first stone / current stone constellation.
You are encouraged to turn the plate. You are not allowed to change any stone placed before.
- Continue in this way, player by player, each taking one turn. If you feel that the garden is complete, or want to sit out one turn, say "pass". The garden is finished when all players say "pass" in a row.
- Silence can contribute to the experience. Whisper if it does not feel right.
- Leaving and returning to the table is welcome.
- What is not explicitly forbidden might be allowed.

1.4. Oral instructions

- Make explicit that this is a collaborative activity to start getting to know each other – there is no winner!
- Read out the written instructions, clarifying in particular that re-entering the game after a pass or retreat is possible. ("When you have passed once but the others have continued to build, you might decide to again add a stone when it's your turn")
- Invite questions. ("What would you like to have clarified or ask?")
- If necessary, clarify open-ended instructions. ("“Until it's right” refers to your personal experience of the stone being placed in an aesthetically pleasing way”; ““What is not explicitly forbidden might be allowed” invites you to use your own judgement when unsure whether a move is permitted.”)
- Announce the time you have allocated for the building phase and that you will introduce additional instructions in case you can see that this time frame is coming to an end.

Additional instructions in case that building exceeds the allocated timeframe:

- “If you have not reached the ‘passing’ phase, you might want to consider what you would need to do to reach that phase”.
- “Now each of you has one more stone to place to finish the garden.”

1.5. Reflection Questions

- Was there a moment that positively surprised you?

- Was there a moment that negatively surprised you?
- Did the game reveal something about yourself to you?

If several groups run the activity simultaneously, reflection questions can be offered to those finishing early to consider quietly or discuss in whispers.

The reflection questions serve two purposes: to create a safe space for sharing and comparing individual experiences, and to surface the strengths that difference can bring to collaboration. Despite the activity's low-stakes nature, builders often develop strong feelings or opinions about how the garden should be constructed – experiences that rarely align completely. The facilitator can lean into this productively. By playfully affirming moments of friction – for instance, “That placement really was outrageous, wasn't it?” – they help create a space where disagreement can be voiced without delegitimizing anyone's choices or perspective. When participants report negative surprises, a simple follow-up question – “And what happened next?” – often prompts them to reflect that what initially felt like an unwelcome move opened up unexpected possibilities. This experience can become a powerful metaphor for collaborative work more broadly.

If desired, the third reflection question can extend this conversation further – inviting participants to explore similarities and differences among group members in more general terms, or in relation to a specific shared assignment ahead.

1.6. Advice for Contextual Adaptations

The activity is broadly applicable to group formation in any context. That said, additional reflection questions can add relevance for specific settings. A few examples:

- **Science or lab contexts:** In groups preparing hands-on experiments that may challenge participants with coordination difficulties or sensory sensitivities, the activity and its reflection questions can open a conversation about how to structure collaboration in ways that enable equal participation for everyone.
- **Qualitative research:** In groups preparing to work with participants, lead qualitative observations, or conduct interviews, the activity can sharpen awareness of how minor changes to a room or setup can be felt strongly – and prompt discussion of the experimental situation from the perspective of those inside it.
- **Design, art, and making:** In groups engaged in the creation or exploration of products, environments, or artworks, the activity can heighten sensitivity to how small differences between objects, arrangements, or spatial configurations can carry significant experiential weight – and animate redesign of elements that might otherwise go unquestioned.

A few final observations:

- **Group size:** We found that the activity works best in groups of up to five participants. For larger groups, consider running it in subgroups before all participants are brought together for a plenary comparison.

- **Repeated use:** The data profile was not designed as a conversation starter only. For example, it might be used at the end of a collaboration to reflect on how the group's dynamics have shifted, making it a tool for both individual and group reflective practice.
- **Language:** While the use of a shared language is advised to avoid communicative obstacles, participants should feel free to respond in whichever language they are most comfortable, particularly in multilingual groups. Facilitators may consider noting this in the written instructions.